

bands at 890–20 and 760–50 cm^{-1} may be due to C–H out-of-plane vibrations⁷.

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Characterisation of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II), Palladium(II) and Platinum(II) Diphenates with Heterocyclic Amines

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THE survey of the literature reveals that diphenic acid has been used as an analytical reagent^{1–4}. The simple metal complexes of diphenic acid have also been studied in solution⁵. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes with diphenic acid (DA) as primary, and quinoline (Q), pyridine (P), 2-aminopyridine (APY) and 2-picoline (Pic) as secondary ligands on the basis of elemental analysis, m.p., conductance, magnetic, infrared and electronic spectral studies.

Experimental

Quinoline was of Riedel-de-Häen AG (Germany), and 2-aminopyridine and 2-Picoline were of I.D.P.L., India. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. The solvents used were obtained from Sisco-Chem. (India) and distilled before use.

Preparation of complexes: Aqueous solutions of metal chlorides (except PdCl_2 which was dissolved in HCl) were mixed with methanolic solutions of diphenic acid and bases in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 : 2 and then refluxed on a water-bath for ≈ 3 h. The mixture was kept overnight in an ice-bath. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed several times with distilled water and finally with methanol, and then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous silica gel.

The results of elemental analysis for the metal and N, m.p. and the values of molar conductances in dimethyl sulphoxide are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	M. p. ($\pm 5^\circ$) °C	Metal	N	Λ_{M} $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
[Cu(DA)(APY)]	315	15.82 (15.97)	6.97 (7.04)	9.29
[Cu(DA)(Q) ₂]	250	11.20 (11.30)	4.93 (4.98)	12.52
[Cu(DA)(P) ₂]	240	13.63 (13.75)	6.00 (6.06)	18.17
[Cu(DA)(Pic) ₂]	>280 d	12.84 (12.97)	5.65 (5.71)	9.07
[Pd(DA)(APY)]	270	23.91 (24.14)	6.28 (6.35)	4.79
[Pd(DA)(Q) ₂]	>360	17.43 (17.59)	4.58 (4.63)	1.86
[Pd(DA)(Pic) ₂]	295	19.78 (19.97)	5.20 (5.25)	2.34
[Pd(DA)(P) ₂]	280	20.91 (21.09)	5.50 (5.50)	14.53
[Pt(DA)(APY)]	>360	36.50 (36.85)	5.24 (5.29)	29.29
[Pt(DA)(Q) ₂]	>360	27.87 (28.13)	3.99 (4.03)	7.90
[Pt(DA)(Pic) ₂]	>360	31.10 (31.39)	4.45 (4.50)	19.10
[Pt(DA)(P) ₂]	>360	32.54 (32.87)	4.67 (4.72)	24.03

*APY = $\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{N}_2$, Q = $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}$, P = $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, Pic = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$,
DA = $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$.
d = decompose.

Physical measurements: Infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer using thin film technique at slow scanning. The electronic spectra were run on a Carl-Zeiss SPECORD uv-vis spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out on a Princeton Applied Research 155 digital vibrating sample magnetometer with an attachment of EG and G, PARC 152 cryogenic temperature controller under a magnetic field of 5000 Gauss produced by a polytropic electromagnet type H.E.M. 200. Conductivity measurements were carried out on a Systronic 302 conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

IR spectra: In the metal complexes of dicarboxylic acids, the shifting of M–O stretching band to a higher frequency is expected to accompany a shift of the C–O stretching band to a lower frequency, together with a shift of the C=O stretching band to a higher frequency. However, there were no pure C–O or M–O stretching modes in the complexes. Nevertheless, linear relationships exist between M–O and the average of ν_1 and ν_7 , i.e. $1/2 [\nu_1 (\text{C=O}) + \nu_7 (\text{C=O})]$. Thus the strong bands at 1700 and 1450 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of diphenic acid due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ were shifted to ≈ 1590 and ≈ 1380 cm^{-1} in Cu^{2+} complexes, ≈ 1600 and ≈ 1450 cm^{-1} in Pd^{2+} complexes, and ≈ 1600 and ≈ 1400 cm^{-1} in Pt^{2+} complexes, respectively. The M–O stretching bands were obtained at 540, 570 and 575 cm^{-1} in the case of Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} and Pt^{2+} complexes, respectively. The

characteristic ring vibrations of the heterocyclic bases in the range 1 600–450 cm⁻¹ generally show significant changes on complexation⁶ which could not be distinguished because of mixing or overlapping with C=O stretching bands. However, the band obtained at 970 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of pyridines shifted to ≈ 990 cm⁻¹ with a gain of intensity in the spectra of their complexes. The in-plane and out-of-plane ring deformation modes observed at ≈ 500 and ≈ 700 cm⁻¹, respectively, are shifted to higher frequencies in mixed ligand complexes indicating their coordination through nitrogen.

Electronic spectra and magnetic studies: All complexes of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} are diamagnetic indicating their square-planar structure while Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic with one unpaired electron. In the case of Cu^{II} complexes three bands at 15 500, 19 500 and 22 000 cm⁻¹ are obtained corresponding to the transitions, ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²E_g and charge-transfer, respectively, which indicate their square-planar stereochemistry⁷. In the case of diamagnetic complexes of d⁸ metal ions, three spin-allowed d-d transitions are anticipated corresponding to the transitions from three lower lying d-orbitals to the empty d_{x²-y²} orbital and the charge transfer bands of lowest energy are expected to involve transitions from the highest filled metal orbitals to the most stable empty ligand, molecular orbital, the a_{2u}(π*). Pd^{II} complexes gave bands at 23 000, 29 300 and 31 500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g, respectively, and one charge transfer band corresponding to the transition a_{1g}(σ*) → a_{2u}(π*) (¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}). Three charge transfer bands at 36 000, 39 500 and 41 000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1u}, π* → a_{2u}(π*), i.e. ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_u and ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u}, respectively, were obtained in the case of Pt^{II} complexes. The last two transitions were from the molecular orbitals localised on the ligands to molecular orbitals localised on the metal and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_u transition was more intense than ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u} transition.

The three orbital parameters Δ₁, Δ₂ and Δ₃ for Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes were calculated⁸ using the orbital and inter-electronic repulsion energies of excited states for d⁸ square-planar complexes (Table 2) for comparison. The separation Δ₁ was the largest which indicated that d_{x²-y²} was much

more strongly antibonded than any of the other d-orbitals. The separation Δ₃ for Pt^{II} complexes was less than for Pd^{II} complexes which indicated that d_{xy} was much more unstable than d_{xz}, d_{yz} in the complexes of Pd^{II} and d_{xy} was much more stable than d_{xz}, d_{yz} in the complexes of Pt^{II}.

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Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Dioxouranium(II) with Thiophene-2-aldehydenicotinic Acid Hydrazone

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METAL complexes of heterocyclic acids and their derivatives, are known for their biological applications. Thus, CNS action of N,N'-diethylnicotinamide¹ and antiinflammatory² and antiulcer³ properties of Cu^{II} complexes of heterocyclic carboxylic compounds have been investigated. Studies on metal complexes of nicotinic acid and related ligands have been reported^{4,5}.

The present paper describes the synthesis of complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and UO₂^{II} with a new bidentate ligand thiophene-2-aldehydenicotinic acid hydrazone (TANAH) which undergoes enolisation in solution prior to complex formation (structures I and II).

TABLE 2—METAL d-ORBITAL ENERGIES FOR Pd^{II} AND Pt^{II} COMPLEXES

Orbital energy differences (cm ⁻¹) for F ₂ - 10F ₄ = 700 cm ⁻¹			
Compd.*	Δ ₁	Δ ₂	Δ ₃
[Pd(DA)(A)] and [Pd(DA)(B) ₂]	25 450	7 700	1 850
[Pt(DA)(A)] and [Pt(DA)(B) ₂]	-	12 000	-3 250

*A = 2-Aminopyridine; B = quinoline, pyridine, 2-picoline.

(I)

(II)